

Mutational Scanning Symposium and Workshop: Event Planning Guide

The University of Washington Department of Genome Sciences, along with the Brotman Baty Institute for Precision Medicine, in Seattle, Washington is the administrative home to the [Atlas of Variant Effects \(AVE\) Alliance](#). The AVE Alliance was founded in 2020 and has grown to include over 800 members from more than 50 countries.

The Mutational Scanning Symposium and Workshop is our flagship annual event that brings together experts in functional genomics, protein science, precision medicine, variant interpretation, and computational genetics. The symposium aims to propel advancements in Multiplex Assays of Variant Effects (MAVEs) and mutational scanning technologies which are crucial for understanding the human genome.

These events provide a platform for researchers to present their work, share new methods, and explore the future of this science. The workshop is dedicated to practical how-to's and deep dives into the technology.

This event planning guide outlines best practices and provides recommendations for organizing, hosting, and running the Mutational Scanning Symposium and Workshop. It includes what the planning committee, lead organizers, and partners need to do before, during, and after the event.

As lead host, you will play a vital role in the planning process, including spearheading efforts to secure sponsorships from local and international organizations.

History of the Mutational Scanning Symposium and the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance

The Mutational Scanning Symposium (and workshop) began in 2017 as a local event in Seattle (pre-dating the Alliance) and was known as the “Deep Mutational Scanning or DMS Symposium”. Early funding for the event came from the Brotman Baty Institute and a NHGRI Center of Excellence in Genome Science Grant (RM1 HG010461), along with a handful of corporate sponsors.

The Atlas of Variant Effects (AVE) Alliance [established in 2020](#), is the organizational host of the Mutational Scanning Symposium. The administrative home for the Alliance is the University of Washington Department of Genome Sciences and the [Brotman Baty Institute](#), Seattle, Washington, USA.

List of Previous Symposiums

1. Deep Mutational Scanning Symposium (DMS17)- Seattle, WA USA
2. Deep Mutational Scanning Symposium (DMS19) - Seattle, WA USA
3. Deep Mutational Scanning Symposium (DMS20)- Seattle, WA USA
4. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS21) - Virtual only
5. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS22)- Toronto, Canada
6. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS23) - Wellcome Sanger, Hinxton, UK
7. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS24) - Broad Institute, Cambridge, MA USA
8. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS25) - Barcelona, Spain
9. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS26) - Melbourne, Australia (planned)
10. Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS27) - Seattle, WA USA (planned)

Table 1: Summary overview of previous Mutational Scanning Symposiums

Year	2017	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Event name	Deep Mutational Scanning Symposium	Deep Mutational Scanning Symposium	Deep Mutational Scanning Symposium	Mutational Scanning Symposium	Mutational Scanning Symposium	Mutational Scanning Symposium	Mutational Scanning Symposium	Mutational Scanning Symposium
Dates (Duration)	11 Sept (1 day)	29 Jan (1 day)	13-14 Jan (2 days)	5-7 Apr (3 days)	14-16 Jun (3 days)	13-14 Jul (2 days)	22-24 May (3 days)	21-23 May (3 days)
Location	UW Seattle USA	UW Seattle USA	UW Seattle USA	Virtual / Online	U of T Toronto Canada	Wellcome Sanger Institute Hinxton UK	Broad Institute, Cambridge USA	IBEC Barcelona Spain
Format	In person	In person	In person and live streamed	Virtual only (no in person activities due to pandemic)	In person and live streamed	In person and live streamed	In person and live streamed	In person and livestreamed
Attendees- In person vs virtual	<u>50</u> All in-person	<u>100</u> All in-person	<u>230</u> All in-person	<u>685</u> All virtual participants	<u>362</u> 133 in-person 229 virtual	<u>407</u> 217 in-person 190 virtual	<u>240</u> 165 in person 75 virtual	<u>310</u> 250 in person 60 virtual
Attendees- countries represented	1	1	5	18	20	50	14	20
Event Registration fees	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Speakers	20	21	21	25	25	34	38	38
Posters	0	25	44	50 (Gathertown)	86 (Gathertown)	84	76	127
Video recordings available on youtube (post-event)	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Event Hashtag	none	none	none	#VariantEffect21	#VariantEffect22	#VariantEffect23	#VariantEffect24	#VariantEffect25

General Event Objectives

- Knowledge Sharing /Training and Education:
 - Provide a platform for and facilitate the exchange of the latest research and methodologies in mutational scanning.
 - Democratize experimental and analytical methods for variant effect mapping.
 - Showcase innovative pre-publication talks on emerging technologies, their [clinical applications](#) and beyond.
 - Offer professional development opportunities for early career scientists.
 - Deliver focused learning and skill-building opportunities through the workshops.
- Community building and networking:
 - Provide opportunities for collaborations.
 - Foster a diverse and inclusive environment.
 - Provide a chance for attendees to engage with (and join) our community.

Process for selecting host/ organizer

The process for selecting the meeting location and lead organizer has been based on expressed interest from a member of the AVE Executive Committee (as well as availability and event support infrastructure from their home institution). In the future, AVE may implement an open application process similar to GA4GH ([GA4GH Plenary meeting co-hosting opportunity](#)), or may decide to select two host institutions with robust event support infrastructure to alternate between on a more consistent basis.

Meeting Dates and Location

Planning starts at least one year in advance. Symposium dates are carefully considered and selected in order to avoid weekends, conflicts with concurrent genomics conferences, major holidays or other dates of cultural significance. In the past, the meeting locations have been the institutional home of the lead organizer.

Typical Venue Requirements

- Capacity: 200-300 attendees
- 3-day availability
- Full AV production equipment and support
- Travel: within one hour by train or car from a major international airport

- Poster session: room for 50 -100 posters
- Accommodations: at the venue itself or within walking distance

Planning / Organizing committee

The planning committee should be diverse and also consist of a balance of more senior and early career researchers. Note: The Director of Program Operations, Lara Muffley, serves on each symposium planning committee in order to provide guidance, continuity, consistency, oversight, and support.

Event Management services/ support

In previous years, we have hired a wedding planner to help organize our event (MSS22 Toronto) and also utilized a part-time event coordinator (MSS24 Boston). Unless you have dedicated institutional event support (like Wellcome Sanger and at IBEC), we recommend hiring a professional event planner or management team. Hiring event management support allows the planning committee to focus on content development, strategic programming, and building meaningful sponsor and speaker relationships—while dramatically reducing stress and operational risks.

Roles and responsibilities - Planning Committee

Much goes into planning for this event. Committee members should expect to wear multiple hats and share tasks flexibly as needs arise. Consider forming subcommittees early in the planning process to help establish who on your team will be responsible for which tasks. Expertise is best directed toward:

- Strategic Decision-Making - Setting event vision, goals, budget, and overall direction
- Content and Programming Development - Designing sessions, workshops, and activities
- Abstract Review and Selection
- Speaker Recruitment and Relations - Identifying, inviting, and supporting keynote speakers, panelists, and presenters
- Fundraising and Sponsorship Relations - Cultivating relationships with sponsors, securing commitments
- Community Building and Networking - Fostering connections among attendees, speakers, and sponsors
- Working closely with the Event Management Team - Articulating needs and providing guidance

Roles and responsibilities - Event Management team

The event management team works in very close coordination with the planning committee.

Note: If an event management group is not available, the Planning Committee will be responsible for executing the tasks below.

- Planning Meetings - Holding regular planning meetings with the full planning committee
- Site Selection - Research meeting venues; request proposals from appropriate facilities and make recommendations
- Budget Management and Financial Reporting - Tracking expenses, managing invoices, and providing regular financial updates
- Registration Services - Managing attendee registration, payments, reimbursements, and communications
- Registration Portal Setup - Building and maintaining the event registration system
- Abstract Collection and Program Management - Collecting and organizing abstracts; assembling the event program
- Presenter and Invited Speaker Support - Coordinating speaker logistics, A/V requirements, and hospitality
- Hotel and Transportation support - Research hotels and lodging options; arranging flights and hotel accommodations for keynotes
- Coordination and Management of Program Publications - Producing printed programs, schedules, and promotional materials
- Meeting Facility Management - Liaising with venues on room setup, A/V, accessibility, and logistics
- Catering Planning - Menu selection, dietary accommodations, and coordination with catering vendors
- Promotion, Publicity, and Marketing Support - Developing and executing marketing campaigns to drive registration
- Special Event and Tour Coordination - Planning receptions, excursions, or ancillary activities
- On-Site Event Coordination - Managing day-of logistics and troubleshooting
- Post-Conference Support - Sending the post event survey to attendees, Compile detailed statistics (final budget, registration #s etc)

Event Landing Page/ Registration Portal

Lead organizers are responsible for arranging for setting up the registration portal and primary event landing page.

Symposium information will also be listed on the AVE Website. <https://www.varianteffect.org/aveevents/>.

Professional event management teams may already have contracts or licenses with CVENT or Swoogo.

Recommended registration fields:

- Full Name (open field)
- Email Address (open field)
- Position: Drop down list:
 - Principal Investigator/Group leader
 - Graduate student

- Undergraduate
- Postdoctoral researcher/fellow
- Faculty (other)
- Mid-career researcher
- Healthcare professional
- Professional staff
- Other (specify)
- Sector: Academia, Government, Industry/for profit, Non- profit, Other (please specify)
- Organization (open field)
- Country or Region (drop down list)
- How did you hear about this event? (open field)
- Dietary restrictions/Preferences (specify) (open field)
- Accessibility Needs: (open field)
- Ticket Type/Registration Category: Virtual, In person, VIP/Speaker
- Session: can choose multiple: e.g. General meeting, Workshop
- Terms and Conditions Agreement: A checkbox requiring agreement to event policies (Abide by our [code of conduct](#))

Registration Fees

Event registration fees have followed a tiered structure that varies annually, ranging from \$0 to \$600 USD. The final fee schedule is determined at the discretion of the organizing committee, taking into account the overall conference budget, anticipated expenses, and the level of external sponsorship secured. These factors help ensure that fees remain fair, accessible, and aligned with the financial sustainability of the event.

Recordings/Youtube

Recordings from previous Mutational Scanning Symposiums are found on [our Youtube Channel](#). The expectation is that future Symposium and Workshop talk recordings will also be made available to the public (if the speaker has granted permission).

Code of Conduct

Organizers are expected to maintain an inclusive, safe, and respectful environment for all attendees.

Organizers must provide a conference code of conduct (<https://www.varianteffect.org/code-of-conduct>) with clearly stated expectations of behavior, systems of reporting, and procedures for addressing inappropriate behavior. The code of conduct and reporting mechanisms should be clear and accessible to all meeting attendees. The planning committee is expected to work out the exact procedures for ensuring the safety of all conference attendees, up to and including removing a perpetrator from the conference. Expectations for behavior are generally communicated during the welcome address (housekeeping / announcements). We also recommend having AVE Code of Conduct Committee “Safety officers” present at the event (identified to participants), along with information on how to report an incident [Code of Conduct Incident Report Form](#).

Inclusion and Accessibility

It is a primary goal of the Alliance to provide inclusive excellence by increasing the involvement of individuals from diverse backgrounds, and underrepresented groups, in the planning, implementation, and participation in the symposium.

Tips for inclusion and accessibility:

- Intentionally select speakers from a variety of backgrounds
- Make sure the planning/organizing committee is diverse
- Offer discounted registration rates / reduce fees for folks in LMIC and who have financial need
- Offer travel / bursary awards to early career scientists
- Make sure to provide clear visa information (general information/ requirements) to international attendees
- Provide inclusive meeting materials / digital content ([UW link](#)/ [EAA](#))
- Provide child care on site, or provide a list of options for local child care
- Include pronouns on badges and online bios (participant provided information/ opt in), (provide stickers at check-in)
- Provide accessible bathrooms (e.g. stalls that can accommodate wheelchairs)
- Provide access to gender inclusive bathrooms
- Include a local Land Acknowledgement (if relevant to region) ([Example from 2022 in Toronto Canada](#))
- Provide support for neurodiverse participants ([Event Professionals Guide to Neuro-inclusive Events](#))
- Enable captioning services / Hire a (virtual or in-person) American Sign Language (ASL) interpreter
- Consider programming in multiple languages
- Consider designating an ‘Event Access Coordinator’ on your team for the event or meeting.
- Have an on site help desk for attendee queries

- Provide a questionnaire (on conference registration websites and registration materials) that will allow participants to voluntarily identify any specific needs, so that conference organizers can make accommodations. (i.e service animal access, wheelchair accessibility, sign language interpretation, reserved front row seat, lactation room access, designated quiet room)

Programming (symposium)

MSS programming typically includes: Featured talks (keynote and invited speakers), Selected talks from abstracts, Short form “flash or lightning talks” (pre-recorded or live), Poster presentations, Unstructured time for networking.

Speakers (including keynotes) are identified by the organizing committee and are selected based on consideration of expertise and background in order to ensure inclusive and diverse programming and perspectives.

Programming (workshop)

MSS programming typically includes companion / satellite workshops dedicated to deep dives into the technology and practical how-to's. Examples from 2025 include: “How to choose a model for variant interpretation and protein design,” and “How to release MAVE datasets that clinicians can use”. The planning committee is responsible for outlining and arranging workshops, including designating or engaging with a workshop coordinator. One effective approach is to solicit workshop ideas and identify hosts through an open Expression of Interest (EOI), inviting self-nominations from community members in advance of the meeting.

Programming (networking)

In feedback from previous years, attendees have expressed a need for unstructured time for opportunities to network. In the agenda, be sure to schedule ample time for coffee breaks and lunch sessions, and organize an evening social event or dinner to facilitate networking and conversations.

Programming (live streaming)

The Symposium and Workshop should be live-streamed for accessibility to virtual registrants (those not able to attend in person for various reasons). Talks (if speakers agree) should be recorded; they will be posted to our youtube channel a few weeks after the event. (Details can be worked out with the event A/V provider).

Posters

Venue/ space must have capacity for 50-100 posters

Recommendation to provide an abstract booklet or collection of posters / abstracts for meeting attendees

Solicit abstract submissions several months in advance of the meeting (set clear deadlines)

Provide and share guidance to poster presenters early

If feasible, offer both print and e-poster options.

Consider Poster awards (establish a rubric, judging process, and certificates)

Event graphics/ Branding

All symposium graphics and materials should include the AVE logo.

Past MSS graphics have been designed by Cris Alexandre, Yvonne Shi, and Sayeh Gorjifard. In past years (2021-2023) we also employed a live conference illustrator ([Alex Cagan](#)) to produce graphics for our event.

We have not specified a consistent branding (color scheme, font etc) for year after year, but we could in the future.

We recommend arranging for or adding a line-item in your budget for graphic design of meeting materials.

Lodging

The recommended conference hotel(s) must be listed on the event website.

Obtain hotel discounts if able (we recommend against securing hotel blocks which require signing a contractual agreement).

Food / event catering

- Consider providing a culturally inclusive menu.
- Provide vegetarian, vegan, gluten-free, and kosher options etc (note: There's a growing trend in event management to default to primarily vegetarian options with 1 vegan and 1 meat alternative).
- Provide all-day beverage service (water, coffee, tea etc).
- Offer alcohol free alternatives /mocktails.
- Work with the caterer to clearly list food ingredients (adjacent to each dish or listed on the website).
- When planning events during Ramadan, be mindful of fasting practices (avoiding food-centric events during daylight hours and providing designated prayer spaces if needed).

Financial / Funding

Support for the Symposium comes primarily from corporate sponsorship and in-kind donations. The average cost to run the 3-day Mutational Scanning Symposium and Workshop is \$100K USD. The AVE Executive Committee members are also expected to contribute to event fundraising. **Please note that the lead event organizer/host is ultimately 'on the hook' for any cost overruns.**

Previous sponsorship has come from: A-Alpha Bio, Abcam, Agilent, Ambry Genetics, AstraZeneca, BioMarin, Brotman Baty Institute for Precision Medicine (BBI) and Center for the Multiplex Assessment of Phenotype (NHGRI CEGS grant), CIFAR, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI), Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG), Congenica, Constantium, Deep Genomics, Dyno Therapeutics, GCATbio, Illumina, Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC), Invitae, La Caixa, Manifold, MAZE, Medicine by Design, Octant, Protocols.io, Revolution Medicines, SGI-DNA, Seismic Therapeutics, Twist, and Wellcome Sanger.

Fundraising should be your first priority for the event. Begin soliciting sponsorships **as early as possible**—ideally > 9 months in advance, before September, when most companies finalize budgets for the following year. Executive involvement is crucial to the fundraising process. All EC members are expected to actively contribute to fundraising efforts. Note that establishing new corporate contacts takes considerable time, so start early and leverage existing relationships where possible. Use our sponsorship prospectus template (available upon request) when approaching potential sponsors to ensure consistent, professional messaging.

Monies are held in an account at the local organizing institution. In the event that there are excess or remaining funds, these would be transferred to the AVE administration's University of Washington Mutational Scanning Conference/revenue budget account.

Meeting Materials

All Symposium and workshop materials are kept in a restricted permissions shared folder on the Alliance Google Drive. This includes templates for post event surveys, speaker agreements, sponsorship requests, etc. These would be available to future organizers to adapt. It is also an expectation that organizers keep all related Symposium/Workshop materials in the shared folder.

Post event survey

Organizers are expected to send out our standardized post -event survey to all attendees. Surveys should go out immediately after the event concludes (within 24 hours or less). Follow up email reminders should be sent out as well. The survey results should be kept in the limited access, secured shared folder.

Data protection / Data privacy

Sharing attendee email lists with event sponsors raises significant ethical and legal considerations, primarily focused on respecting individual privacy and adhering to data protection regulations like GDPR. In compliance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) rules and for best practice, organizers should not share or distribute attendee or registration lists (names/emails) - even to sponsors who request this. Information on registrants or attendees should reside on a secure server, behind a firewall, and be accessible only to event organizers and the AVE executive committee. Privacy policies should be disclosed during the registration process.

Pre and Post Event Press:

The AVE communications manager and BBI Director of Communications will be partnering with your local institution and communications team to promote the event. Examples of promotional work from previous years:

- [Building an atlas of gene variants to understand health and disease](#)
- [Following Up on MSS 2023: Perspectives from Two Participants](#)
- [Q&A with Invited speaker Dr. Xiaoyan “Isaac” Jia](#)
- [What to Expect at the MSS 2023 Symposium July 13 and 14 in UK: A Q&A with Keynote Speaker Dr. Frederick \(Fritz\) Roth](#)
- [MSS 2023 Planners Explore Expected Symposium Highlights and Opportunities with Drs. Clare Turnbull and David Adams](#)
- [Spotlight on MSS 2025: Lindorff-Larsen to Address Symposium on Interface Between Variant Effects and Interpretation](#)
- [MSS 2025 Update: BioMarin Sponsorship Aims to Drive Progress in Development of Therapies for Rare Diseases](#)

Channels utilized for promoting the event include BBI and AVE accounts for Bluesky, LinkedIn , as well as our websites and newsletters.

Post event

After the event concludes, provide a brief summary to AVE’s Executive Committee and Director of Program Operations. The summary should include: attendance metrics, budget/expenditures, lessons learned, symposium highlights and photos and post-event survey results. All materials should be kept on the secured AVE Shared Drive.

Event planning checklist

This list is not exhaustive, but just meant to serve as a general guide for planning and preparation.

Process	Timing	Steps
Planning and Preparation	As least 12mo prior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Express your interest in being the lead host for the Mutational Scanning Symposium <input type="checkbox"/> Meet with AVE’s Director of Program Operations (Lara Muffley) to discuss the planning process, timeline and to gain access to templates and materials in the shared drive. <input type="checkbox"/> Identify and convene the event planning committee (include AVE’s Director of Program Operations and a long standing member of the Executive Committee for continuity) <input type="checkbox"/> Consider symposium and workshop objectives & goals <input type="checkbox"/> Brainstorm and determine the program ‘theme’ <input type="checkbox"/> Mock up a budget <input type="checkbox"/> Contemplate hiring an event planner/ organizer or event management company to assist you (unless you have institutional event support) <input type="checkbox"/> Set up regular meetings (~1x a month to start with increasing frequency as event draws near) <input type="checkbox"/> Map out an event planning timeline <input type="checkbox"/> Set up planning space(s) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Shared documents folder in the AVE shared drive <input type="checkbox"/> Slack channel (within AVE) <input type="checkbox"/> Trello board, Notion, or google sheet/doc <input type="checkbox"/> Review previous years ‘lessons learned’ docs and post event survey results <input type="checkbox"/> Prepare a detailed draft budget for all expenses related to the event (preferably before venue/ dates are locked in) <input type="checkbox"/> Create a “local” account to receive incoming donations and registration fees <input type="checkbox"/> Research venue and dates <input type="checkbox"/> Secure venue and lock in the dates <input type="checkbox"/> Start a list of possible speakers and workshop presenters <input type="checkbox"/> Invite keynote and select speakers

		<input type="checkbox"/> Compile a list of potential sponsors <input type="checkbox"/> Create a sponsorship strategy and prospectus <input type="checkbox"/> Start sending sponsorship requests/asks <input type="checkbox"/> Send out “Save the Date” notices
	8mo	<input type="checkbox"/> Research any required event suppliers. (caterers, photographers, etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Line-up event technology partners (A/V, production support) <input type="checkbox"/> Employ a graphic designer or ask for a talented volunteer to produce symposium graphics/ materials <input type="checkbox"/> Create the registration portal and main event website/ landing page (this is separate than the AVE website event page) <input type="checkbox"/> Set up an event specific email address (and designate someone to monitor the account)
	6mo	<input type="checkbox"/> Mock up a detailed agenda <input type="checkbox"/> Set up an online registration system (if you haven't already). <input type="checkbox"/> Announce the open registration (consider early bird discounts) <input type="checkbox"/> Set aside a handful of VIP “tickets” <input type="checkbox"/> Call for Abstracts <input type="checkbox"/> Confirm speakers, obtain biographies, photos, titles of talks, session overviews, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Continue reaching out to potential sponsors and secure funding <input type="checkbox"/> Finalize event branding and design – theme, logos, colors, etc. in consultation with AVE’s Director of Program Operations and in consultation with the AVE EC. <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing: Promote the event through your institutional networks, social media, etc (in close coordination with AVE’s Communications Manager and BBI’s Director of Communications)
	3mo	<input type="checkbox"/> Finalize the agenda <input type="checkbox"/> Select abstracts / notify presenters

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Send poster presentation information and instructions to presenters <input type="checkbox"/> Create speakers agreement /permissions (to photograph, record, upload talks to youtube) <input type="checkbox"/> Line up any entertainment (music during dinner?) <input type="checkbox"/> Lock in sponsors (signed contracts), continue reaching out to more if needed. <input type="checkbox"/> Obtain sponsor logos <input type="checkbox"/> Identify and reach out to moderators and other event volunteers <input type="checkbox"/> Compile and add content to the event website, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Agenda <input type="checkbox"/> sponsor logos <input type="checkbox"/> speaker headshots and bios <input type="checkbox"/> Event location (venue-exhibit hall map), lodging options <input type="checkbox"/> Transportation/parking info <input type="checkbox"/> Registration (fees and link to register) <input type="checkbox"/> Important dates/deadlines (registration, abstract submissions etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Contact information (event specific email address) <input type="checkbox"/> Plan /consider event decorations or signage <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinate with sponsors/ Do they need a table or booth? <input type="checkbox"/> Continue to announce and promote event <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Send out a press release (build excitement about program/speakers etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Plan LinkedIn and social media posts (using the official event #hashtag, etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Make updates to website (event landing page)
	1mo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Create Symposium Slide Decks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Housekeeping slides code of conduct <input type="checkbox"/> Announcement or informational slides to play during breaks <input type="checkbox"/> Provide detailed instructions to speakers, moderators, volunteers <input type="checkbox"/> Obtain Speaker agreements (permission to record etc)

		<input type="checkbox"/> Continue to announce and promote event <input type="checkbox"/> Send reminders to everyone who's registered so far (1mo, 1 wk, 1d before)
	Day of Event	<input type="checkbox"/> Ensure all AV equipment is functional <input type="checkbox"/> Check in with catering <input type="checkbox"/> Arrange seating and signage <input type="checkbox"/> Set up registration desks with name badges and event materials <input type="checkbox"/> Ensure staff or volunteers are available to staff the registration desk <input type="checkbox"/> Start with a welcome address by the organizing committee <input type="checkbox"/> Include housekeeping remarks and expectations for conduct <input type="checkbox"/> Outline the event's objectives and agenda <input type="checkbox"/> Provide clear instructions for workshop participants <input type="checkbox"/> Ensure all sessions are recorded for future reference <input type="checkbox"/> Arrange for live event press/ social media posts
	Post Event	<input type="checkbox"/> Send out a post event survey (immediately after the event concludes) along with follow up email reminders <input type="checkbox"/> Share event highlights and recordings with participants <input type="checkbox"/> Follow up/ thank you's to all speakers <input type="checkbox"/> Follow up/ thank you's to all sponsors (in coordination with next year's organizers) <input type="checkbox"/> Review and pay outstanding invoices <input type="checkbox"/> Reconcile expenses, costs, incidentals, etc. against conference budget <input type="checkbox"/> Prepare a post-event report summarizing key takeaways, attendance statistics, and financials <input type="checkbox"/> Meet with organizing committee for a debrief <input type="checkbox"/> Make a list of lessons learned and hand off the baton to next year's organizers

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